

Anti-Alcohol Education in the Secondary Education Curriculum of Nepal

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Abstract

Nepal's secondary education curriculum has integrated an anti-alcohol education into various subjects' curricula. For instance, the curriculum of some important subjects (health and physical education, sociology, hotel management, human value education, social study and science and technology) related to human daily life and social life includes content about anti-alcohol education. However, the extent of anti-alcohol education content within these subjects remains unclear. The primary purpose of this study is to examine the place and nature of anti-alcohol education in Nepal's secondary education curriculum. The secondary education curriculum and syllabus were reviewed by using the qualitative content analysis method. The main findings of this study reveal that the curriculum for secondary-level subjects (grade 9 to 12), such as science and technology, social studies and life skills education, sociology, hotel management, health and physical education, and human value education, include contents on alcohol education. Even though the curriculum consists of contents related to alcohol education, its scope appears limited. While some subjects' curricula include measures to control alcohol, others only mention the use of alcohol as a cause of non-communicable diseases. So, it is said that in the secondary education curriculum, little attention has been paid to incorporating anti-alcohol education.

Keywords: *alcohol, anti-alcohol education, content analysis, curriculum, secondary education, syllabus*